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ABCA3 functions in multi-drug resistance in human cancer in metastasis to the bone.

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We describe here a function for the ATP-binding cassette gene *ABCA3* in multi-drug resistance in human cancer (1-3), supported by evidence by demonstrating its transcriptional up-regulation with significance at the transcriptome level in metastasis to distant organ sites in human breast cancer (4, 5), and by separate evidence demonstrating that ATP-binding cassette genes function in multi-drug resistance: in resistance to a platinum agent, in resistance to doxorubicin, and in resistance to paclitaxel (2).

1 **Results**

2 **Figure 1:** ABCA3 is differentially expressed in the bone metastases of humans with breast cancer.

3 I. Metastasis to the bone in humans with breast cancer.

4 *n*=3 MCF7 (human; breast cancer)
5 *n*=3 MCF7b bone metastatic variant

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GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
21	2.41E-05	0.05	-4.223453	-0.2109832	4538.81	ABCA3	5752/20047	71.3

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8 Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in human breast cancer cells (MCF7) and a
9 metastatic MCF7 variant, MCF7b, we discovered differential expression of ATP binding cassette subfamily
10 A member 3, encoded by *ABCA3* in metastasis to the bone in breast cancer (**Chart 1**). The expression of
11 *ABCA3* changed more than 70% of the human breast cancer transcriptome when considering all
12 transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 20,047 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative
13 fold-change indicating increased quantity of *ABCA3* messenger RNA in breast cancer bone metastasis,
14 demonstrating up-regulation of *ABCA3* during disease progression and metastasis.

13 **Discussion**

14 We described here transcriptional induction of a gene with functions in multi-drug resistance, in
15 bone metastasis in human breast cancer. Novel approaches to challenging metastasis and resistance will
16 utilize chemotherapy in conjunction with i) kinase and phosphatase inhibitors targeted to tissue and tumor
17 type whose functions overlap with that of growth factor and growth factor receptor inhibitors, ii) inhibitors of
18 the ATP-binding cassette family (multi-drug resistance pumps), and iii) CDK4/6 inhibitors, which function
19 as senescence-inducing agents.

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1 **References**

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Methods

We measured total transcription in primary tumors and metastasis to distant organ sites including the bones, the brain, the liver and the lungs using microarray and RNA-sequencing datasets (GSEXXXXX and GSEXXXXX) and R-based computational software for exact quantitative determination of multi-drug resistant pump transcriptional induction at the transcriptome level.